

An Assessment of Compulsive Smartphone Usage and Mental Health among Indian Adolescents

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Lately in India, the rapid transition of smartphones from a luxury communication device to an important instrument for social connectivity has led to a significant increase in compulsive usage among adolescents. This transition was fast-tracked by the post-pandemic shift to online learning, which has made the device a fundamental "survival tool" that deeply influences mental health. Stratified random sampling was used to select 247 out of 400 12th-grade students of Bhopal and to evaluate mental health. The data was collected using the Compulsive Smartphone Use Scale (CSUS) constructed by the researchers consulting the SAS (Kwon et al., 2013) and the NMP-Q (Yildirim & Correia, 2015) questionnaires and the mental health was assessed using an instrument adapted from the 28-item General Health Questionnaire (GHQ-28), which was originally derived from the GHQ-60 (Goldberg & Hillier, 1979). The findings revealed that the Academic Stream is a primary predictor of compulsive usage, with Arts-Commerce students exhibiting higher levels of technological and psychological dependency than their science peers. Female students got higher academic grades but reported a significantly higher cumulative burden of mental health distress particularly regarding social dysfunction and somatic symptoms. Further, it was found that compulsive usage is a robust predictor of anxiety, insomnia, and depression, with usage often serving as a "digital compensation" for real-world social anxieties. Young people should be guided to recognize the "Perception-Performance Gap," where the smartphone is often mistakenly credited for academic management while simultaneously undermining internal stability. For this, educational institutions should implement gender-sensitive mental health interventions and digital literacy programs so that technology remains a boon rather than a psychological hindrance. True autonomy and self-regulation should be fostered within students rather than relying on compulsive digital escapes.

Keywords: Compulsive smartphone usage (CSU), adolescent mental health, psychological distress

Today, smartphones are no longer just luxury items but are now essential for social and educational life. For many adolescents, this has led to compulsive use, often called smartphone addiction or dependence (Bhandari et al., 2021). This constant urge to stay connected is more than a habit; it is reinforced by changes in the brain's reward pathways (Volkow et al., 2019).

The impact of the compulsive smartphone usage on adolescent mental health is deep and multifaceted and longitudinal research has demonstrated that excessive screen time, mostly exceeding three hours daily is a significant risk factor for the development of anxiety and depressive symptoms (Berke & Hyman, 2000). In the post-pandemic environment, the relationship between smartphone addiction and reduced life satisfaction has become more pronounced, as digital over-reliance often displaces critical face-to-face social interactions and healthy sleep patterns (Zhu et al., 2025). If we talk in the Indian context, studies are showing that female adolescents, especially those in urban environments, may be at a higher risk for psychological distress associated with smartphone

overuse (Koob & Volkow, 2016). Understanding these dynamics is essential for developing interventions that protect the Mental Health of the next generation.

The transition of the smartphone from a communication tool to an indispensable social artifact has given rise to the phenomenon of compulsive usage, often conceptualized as "Problematic Smartphone Use" (PSU) or smartphone addiction (Mason et al., 2022). Recent global data underscores a significant surge in addictive digital behaviors and confirms that many research studies have reported that a lot of adolescents worldwide now show addiction-like symptoms, like an inability to control compulsive smartphone usage and withdrawal when trying to control it. This trend is mirrored in localized studies like longitudinal research in China, which hinted that the pooled prevalence of smartphone dependence among adolescents has reached 27% by 2025, significantly outpacing adult populations due to underdeveloped impulse control in younger users (Sohn et al., 2021).

The relationship between compulsive smartphone usage and its negative impacts on mental and emotional states is a well-researched topic. Research done by Nawaz (2024) found that adolescents with high Problematic Smartphone Usage scores are nearly three times more likely to experience clinical symptoms of depression and twice as likely to suffer from anxiety compared to non-problematic users. This is often attributed to "displacement theory," where digital engagement replaces face-to-face social interactions, leading to increased feelings of loneliness and social isolation (Salepaki et al., 2025). Beyond psychological distress, compulsive usage has been linked to structural and functional changes in the brain. Neuroimaging studies have provided preliminary insights into

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deficits in executive function and cognitive control among adolescents with high smartphone engagement (Yogesh et al., 2024). Research conducted across several countries highlighted that smartphone addiction is a primary driver of poor sleep quality, with a mean Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) score of 7.26 among heavy users, showing significant sleep disturbance (Giansanti, 2025). In research works done in India, gender-specific patterns have emerged, as Pandya et al. (2021) observed that in their study, in urban cities like Ahmedabad, female students showed a slightly higher frequency of addiction (57%) compared to boys (43%), which is often motivated by a higher trust in smartphones for social validation and interpersonal communication. On the other hand, some studies have found that while the risk is high across all genders, the motivations for the phone's usage differ as boys are seen as being more susceptible to gaming-related addiction and girls to social media-induced anxiety (Izquierdo-Condoy et al., 2024).

Relevance of the Study

The adolescents are experiencing fragmentation and high pressure because of the rapid technological developments and the hectic lifestyles in the contemporary world (Odgers & Jensen, 2020). In chasing a better lifestyle and professional success, the Youngsters are leaving behind the warmth of the age-old social support systems, which were the basis of positive mental well-being (Campbell et al., 2016). Because of the transition to omnipresent mobile connectivity that has now flooded India, resulting in shifting of social networks and creating a setting where professional and academic demands often lead to seclusion and a lack of genuine happiness.

The relevance of this study lies in knowing how this digital shift has transformed the smartphone into a "survival tool" for social networking, frequently resulting in Compulsive Smartphone Usage (CSU). This research is so important now given the mental state of school students after the pandemic, because the forced need for smartphones has created a difficult circumstance, as it serves as a primary doorway for connectivity but still it acts as a major reason for causing anxiety, insomnia, and social dysfunction. And to protect the mental health of the next generation in an increasingly lonely and high-velocity digital world, understanding these problems is essential for developing awareness programs, counselling interventions, etc. (Wood et al., 2023).

Objectives of the Study

- The objective of this study was to examine the effects of compulsive Smartphone usage on the mental health of male and female 12th grade students.
- The objective of this study was to examine the association between compulsive smartphone usage and mental health among male and female students across various academic streams.

Method

Participants and Research Design

For this study, 400 12th-grade students were randomly selected, out of which only 247 participants enrolled in schools affiliated with the Central Board of Secondary Education (CBSE) from Bhopal city, Madhya Pradesh, who fulfilled the pre-defined inclusion criteria. A 2x2 factorial design was used to categorize students by Gender (Male & Female) and academic stream of course (Science & Arts-Commerce).

Measures

The data for this study was collected by a survey method using a questionnaire, which was divided into three sections designed to capture comprehensive information from the participants. Section A consists of demographic items related to age, gender, and socioeconomic status. Section B utilized the Compulsive Smartphone Use Scale to quantify the severity of students' smartphone dependency. Finally, Section C included a Mental Health Scale. A brief description of these measures is given below-

Compulsive Smartphone Use Scale (CSUS) was constructed after consulting the Smartphone Addiction Scale (SAS) by Kwon et al. (2013) and the Nomophobia Questionnaire (NMP-Q) by Yildirim and Correia (2015) for the Indian context. It's a 5-point Likert scale ("Never" to "Very often") covering four domains that are Time/Overuse, Psychological/Social, Preoccupation, and Technological. The scores range from 20 to 100, with higher values indicating greater compulsion. The Compulsive Smartphone Use Scale (CSUS) demonstrated high internal consistency with a Cronbach's alpha of $\alpha = 0.86$, establishing it as a reliable and valid instrument for measuring addictive digital behaviors within this adolescent sample.

The Mental Health Scale (MHS) was used to collect the data. The scale is a 20-item adaptation of the General Health Questionnaire (GHQ-28) which was originally derived from the GHQ-60 Goldberg and Hillier, 1979 rated on a five-point Likert scale with 5 (*strongly agree*) for highest and 1 (*strongly disagree*) for lowest. Total scores range from 20 to 100, with higher scores indicating poorer mental health. The MHS demonstrated high internal consistency with a Cronbach's alpha of $\alpha = 0.859$, establishing it as a reliable and valid instrument for measuring mental health of adolescents.

Procedure

Data collection was carried out after the COVID-19 logistical constraints were lifted and the study's methodology was modified to analyze and compare the impact of smartphones on 12th grade students before and after their transition to online learning. Once in-person classes resumed, the researcher took permission from private secondary schools in the city of Bhopal. Data integrity and ethical agreement were ensured by following a standardized data collection protocol where students were told their identity would be kept private and instructions were read aloud under teacher supervision to maintain uniform comprehension across all sites.

Data Analysis

Exploratory analysis was conducted using measures of central tendency, including means, modes, and standard deviations, to examine the distribution and nature of scores across the four domains of the Compulsive Smartphone Use Scale (CSUS) and the four sub-dimensions of the Mental Health Scale (MHS) and to find the strength and direction of the relationship between behavioral aspect of compulsive smartphone usage and psychological/mental well-being the Pearson's product-moment correlation coefficients were calculated. The analysis done in this study focused on the interaction between CSU total scores and mental health outcomes such as anxiety, insomnia, depression, and somatic symptoms. A 2x2 factorial ANOVA was applied to investigate the main effects and interaction effects of the independent variables Gender (Male & Female) and Academic Stream (Science & Arts-Commerce). To identify the most significant behavioral predictors of mental health,

stepwise multiple regression was performed and this determined the specific percentage of variance in anxiety, insomnia, depression, and somatic symptoms explained by various components of compulsive smartphone usage.

Results

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 shows the summary of the demographic characteristics of

students, which were analysed using descriptive statistics. In Table 1, we can see that male students are higher in number in the Science stream (45.5%) than females (37.9%), whereas females (62.1%) are more in number than males (54.4%) in the Arts-Commerce stream. When we look at Smartphone ownership, 95.9% of males and 96.8% of females own a smartphone; the remaining students used phones of family members. When we talk about the duration of ownership, 43.9% of students said that they have their phone for less than two years, meanwhile 42.3% said they have their smartphone for two to five years.

Table 1
Depiction of Sample Characteristics in Percentages

Characteristics	Group	Males (n=123)	Females (n=124)	Total (N=247)
Academic Stream	Science	45.5%	37.9%	41.7%
	Arts-Commerce	54.5%	62.1%	58.3%
Smartphone Ownership	Yes	95.9%	96.8%	96.0%
	No	4.1%	3.2%	4.0%
Daily Usage Frequency	Less than 20 times	41.5%	33.1%	37.2%
	20-40 times	41.5%	40.3%	40.9%
	More than 40 times	17.1%	26.6%	21.9%

When the economic analysis of phone ownership showed significant gender-based disparities. Males are significantly higher in number when it comes to owning devices costing over ₹20,000 (48.8% vs. 37.9%), meanwhile, females fall into ₹10,000 to ₹20,000 device cost bracket. Now, while both genders are seen going for budget-friendly monthly recharge amount which are usually under ₹500, it was observed that more female students than male students (8.9% vs. 4.1%) subscribed to higher-cost recharge plans exceeding ₹2000 per month. Daily usage patterns showed that females indicated a more frequent engagement, where 26.6% of females reported using their smartphones more than 40 times per day compared to only 17.1% of male students. Males reported infrequent usage of smartphone engaging with their device fewer than 20 times daily (41.5%).

Inferential Statistics

To examine the relationships as well as the differences between variables, inferential statistics were used in this study. The intercorrelations (Pearson's r) between the five components of Compulsive Smartphone Use (CSU) and the four components of the Mental Health Scale (MHS) can be seen in Table 2 with their respective total scores. The inferential analysis showed moderate but significant correlation strongly linking higher Compulsive

Smartphone Usage with poorer mental health outcomes. The CSU Total Score shows a highly significant positive correlation with the Mental Health Scale Total scores. This is the strongest correlation in the entire table, indicating that higher overall levels of compulsive smartphone usage are strongly associated with higher total mental health symptom severity (poorer mental health). The CSU Total Score is also significantly correlated with all individual components of mental health, most notably Anxiety, Insomnia and Somatic Symptoms. The individual components of CSU are significantly correlated with specific mental health components. The mental health component Anxiety and Insomnia show the highest correlations across all CSU components, particularly with Preoccupation and Psychological/Social usage. This suggests that compulsive thinking about the smartphone and using it for social/psychological regulation are key drivers of anxiety and sleep difficulties. All CSU components, except Technological, are significantly correlated with Somatic Symptoms. The strongest relationship is with Time and Overuse, indicating that physical complaints (e.g., headache, neck pain) are more closely tied to the amount of time spent on the device. The MH component Depression shows the strongest correlation with the CSU Total Score and the Preoccupation component.

Table 2
Intercorrelations between Compulsive Smartphone Usage and Mental Health

Components of CSU	Somatic Symptoms	Anxiety and Insomnia	Social Dysfunction	Depression	MHS Total Scores
Time & Overuse	.35**	.35**	-.24**	.24**	.35**
Psychological/Social	.32**	.35**	-.30**	.26**	.36**
Preoccupation	.35*	.38**	-.21**	.29**	.41**
Technological	.14*	.15*	-.18**	.08	.12
CSU Total Score	.39**	.42**	-.30**	.31**	.43**

Note. * ($p < .05$), ** ($p < .01$)

Interestingly, all CSU components show a significant negative correlation with Social Dysfunction as presented in Table 2. The strongest negative relationship is with Psychological/Social usage ($r=-.30^{**}$). This finding suggests that students with higher compulsive use, particularly for social/psychological reasons, tend to report less social dysfunction, possibly because the smartphone itself acts as a channel for social maintenance or reduces the perception of real-world social difficulties. The Technological component of CSU shows the weakest overall relationship with mental health symptoms ($r=.12$). It is significantly correlated with Somatic Symptoms ($r=.14^*$), Anxiety and Insomnia ($r=.15^*$), and Social Dysfunction ($r=-.18^{**}$), but shows no significant correlation with the Mental Health Scale Total score ($r=.12$), or Depression ($r=.08$), and this means that compulsive usage driven purely by the smartphone's features as opposed to time spent on it or psychological preoccupation, is the least impactful cause of severe mental health distress.

The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) in Table 3 shows that the Academic Stream is a primary predictor of Compulsive Smartphone Usage (CSU), with a highly significant main effect on both the total/whole scale and specific sub-dimensions. Students in the Arts-Commerce stream reported significantly higher mean scores than their science peers, and this trend was mostly driven by high dependence in the Technological and Psychological/Social components of CSU. That is specifically the Technological

component that showed the heartiest main effect, suggesting that students in the Arts-Commerce stream experience greater preoccupation with the smartphone's functionalities and applications. Now, on the other hand Gender did not appear as a statistically significant factor influencing CSU because female students reported only marginal and non-significant increases in mean scores across most dimensions of CSU. In contrast to behavioral usage patterns, the analysis of Mental Health Scale (MHS) scores identifies Gender as the central significant variable, as we can see in Table 4. It was also seen that female students showed a significantly high collective burden of psychological/mental distress compared to male students, a disparity primarily attributed to the Social Dysfunction component, where females scored significantly higher. Even though females also displayed obviously high mean scores for somatic symptoms, anxiety, and depression, these individual differences did not reach statistical significance and their collective impact led to a significantly high total MHS score.

The underlying relationships between this research paper's major variables were examined and for that a comprehensive correlational analysis was conducted using Pearson's product-moment correlation coefficients. The results of the analysis showed a dependable pattern of statistically significant positive correlations deeply linking higher levels of Compulsive Smartphone Usage (CSU) with higher mental health dysfunction. The total CSU score came out as the strongest predictor showing its strongest positive relations with Anxiety and

Table 3

ANOVA Result Depicting Mean Differences on Compulsive Smartphone Usage as a Function Of Academic Stream and Gender

Components of Compulsive Smartphone Use	Academic stream				F (1,243)		Gender				F (1,243)
	Science		Arts-Commerce		Male		Female				
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD			
Time and Overuse	16.89	4.66	18.63	5.62	6.13	17.47	5.03	18.33	5.55	0.96	
Psychological/Social	15.96	4.52	17.83	5.33	7.97*	16.84	4.46	17.25	5.64	0.25	
Preoccupation	16.79	5.10	18.67	5.36	6.91	17.18	5.13	18.58	5.44	3.41	
Technological	1.32	0.83	1.79	1.24	11.17**	1.60	1.04	1.59	1.19	0.89	
Overall CSU	50.96	12.61	56.91	14.40	10.61**	53.10	12.50	55.75	15.22	0.21	

Note. * ($p < .05$), ** ($p < .01$)

Table 4

ANOVA Result Depicting Mean Differences In Mental Health as a Function of Academic Stream and Gender

Components of Mental Health	Academic stream				F (1,243)		Gender				F (1,243)
	Science		Arts-Commerce		Male		Female				
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD			
Somatic Symptoms	13.27	4.65	13.26	4.11	0.030	12.72	4.15	13.80	4.47	3.59	
Anxiety and Insomnia	14.42	4.60	14.47	4.28	0.003	13.89	4.21	15.01	4.54	3.67	
Social Dysfunction	2.90	1.18	2.86	1.30	0.209	2.72	1.24	3.02	1.24	4.16*	
Depression	12.51	4.74	12.61	4.46	0.002	12.13	4.55	13.01	4.56	2.17	
Overall MHS	53.65	14.81	53.81	12.73	0.014	51.33	13.11	56.13	13.72	7.65*	

Note. * ($p < .05$), ** ($p < .01$)

A negative correlation was observed (Table 2) between all the components or dimensions of CSU and Social Dysfunction even though most of the mental health dimensions showed deterioration with increased usage. This reverse relationship was most obvious in the Psychological/Social dimension ($r=-.30^{**}$), which may be because the smartphone serves as a persistent network for digital social preservation or acts as a cover-up for real-world interactive difficulties and as a result, compulsive users may perceive lower

social impairment. In contrast, the Technological component of CSU representing dependency driven by specific device features rather than psychological need, exhibited the weakest overall association with mental health outcomes. While it remained correlated with somatic and anxiety symptoms, it showed no significant link to depression or the total mental health scale score, indicating that purely feature-driven use is the least impactful factor in severe psychological distress.

Table 5

Step-wise Regression of CSU Predicting Overall Mental Health

Total CSU	Somatic symptoms			Anxiety and Insomnia			Social dysfunction			Depression			Overall CSU		
	R	R ²	β	R	R ²	β	R	R ²	β	R	R ²	β	R	R ²	β
Scale Scores	.27	.07	.12	.42	.18	.13	.30	.09	.07	.31	.10	.10	.43	.19	.43

The stepwise regression analyses conducted to identify the behavioral predictors of mental health outcomes as can be seen in Table 5 revealed that overall Compulsive Smartphone Usage (CSU) emerged as a significant predictor of all four components of Mental Health ($R^2=.19$) like Somatic Symptoms, Anxiety and Insomnia, Social Dysfunction, and Depression.

Discussion

In this study, the relationship between compulsive smartphone usage (CSU) and mental health was explored among 12th grade students in the city of Bhopal. The analysis gave an interesting look at how the digital dependency of the smartphone and its effects on Mental Health in the post-pandemic scenario are influenced by academic stream and gender (Taddi et al., 2024). The academic stream significantly predicted CSU, where students in the Arts and Commerce streams showed higher levels of compulsion than students in the Science stream. This may be because the Science curriculum (PCM/Biology) is very structured and demands a lot of time and that is why they are unable to use their device compulsively. On the other hand, it was observed that Arts and Commerce students are preoccupied with their smartphone may be because they have greater dependence on digital platforms for forming social connections and for their creative expression and that is why they scored high on "Technological" and "Psychological/Social" dimensions. The recent study done by Abed et al. (2017) shows that adolescents in India, particularly living in urban areas, often use smartphones as a basic tool for social validation, which is a behavior that fluctuates based on the student's daily academic thoroughness and available leisure time.

Students, especially females, showed significantly higher mental distress, particularly in the domain of social dysfunction. This "gender incongruity" where usage levels are similar but psychological impact differs is supported by Machado et al. (2023) who say that female adolescents are more vulnerable to the emotional distress and "fear of missing out" (FOMO) that is very much rampant on social media. The results of this study indicate that digital stress is more likely to manifest as a bodily issue in adolescent girls, as can be seen by their scoring high on dimensions related to somatic symptoms and anxiety. It was confirmed that CSU is a strong predictor of anxiety, insomnia, and depression through regression analysis done in this study. Specifically, the variance

explained by anxiety and insomnia dimension stresses what was found in a study done by Alahdal et al. (2023) that blue light coming from using smartphones late at night upsets circadian rhythms.

A major finding in this study was that an opposite relationship between CSU and social dysfunction domain was observed because compulsive users reported that they did not experience social impairment and this could be because students may be using smartphones to cover up real life social pressures by managing a strong digital social life. According to Yogesh et al. (2024), a sense of belongingness is felt as smartphones work as a medium or a channel for being always socially connected, even when we know that it simultaneously contribute in internalizing symptoms like depression.

From the results of interaction analysis it was observed that compulsive usage was mostly seen in males belonging to Arts-Commerce academic stream and it could be because Arts-commerce stream has less rigid academic structure and that male adolescents are may be more likely to be addicted to the technological features of a smartphone such as gaming or high-frequency app switching while on the other hand it was seen that females were able to maintain a more consistent level of smartphone usage across different academic streams.

Recommendations

Schools and colleges can implement wide-ranging digital literacy programs that go beyond teaching technical skills to address the negative psychological effects of Compulsive Smartphone Usage. These programs can help students understand that what they are thinking as functional "Academic Management" is not serving them and "Time and Overuse" that is smartphones' compulsive usage is driven by the need for instant digital "likes" and rewards (Mason et al., 2014). The transition to digitally integrated learning must be balanced with the restoration of real-world avenues for satisfying fundamental psychological needs (Bauwens et al., 2020). Since the smartphone often serves as a surrogate for autonomy, competence, and relatedness, educators and parents should collaborate to create non-digital spaces where students can experience achievement and social validation without the pressure of social media or parental disapproval (Qayyum et al., 2024). Reducing reliance on smartphones as an escape mechanism requires shifting the educational focus towards a more wholesome peer collaboration and

social academic connectivity and according to Weiss et al. (2025), Indian schools and colleges need mental health support that addresses the different needs of male and female students. Our research finds that female students often keep up strong academic performance even though they experience more anxiety and sleep problems than others and Counseling programs should focus on the mental health risks that come from compulsive smartphone usage and intense academic competition to be truly helpful (Torous et al. 2025). These interventions should focus on bridging the gap between objective performance and subjective well-being so that students are better able to manage their internal emotional stability through these recommendations that is often undermined by compulsive habits.

Limitations of the Study

The limitations of this study primarily involve its geographic and institutional scope, as the sample consisted of 12th-grade students from CBSE-affiliated private schools in Bhopal city and excluded the rural or government school population. In this study, the testing of the extent of impact of Compulsive Smartphone Usage on Mental Health and Academic functioning comes with potential Social desirability bias, which is usually observed whenever a self-reported questionnaire is used to gather data, because students might underreport addictive behaviors and sometimes overstate their mental well-being. The cross-sectional design of this study also stops the establishment of definitive causal links. While CSU predicts mental health distress, it is unclear if usage causes distress or if existing distress drives compulsive usage as a coping mechanism (Kutty & Sreeramareddy, 2014). But the study's focus on the post-pandemic scene shows an inimitable historical context that cannot be applied to future cohorts who will never experience the shift from offline to online learning.

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